

Marketing Ethics in South East Nigeria

Ogbuke, J. C., Ejionueme, N. & Nebo, G. N.

Abstract

The study was on the assessing marketing ethics in South East Nigeria. The specific goals include to: evaluate the effect of product safety on the marketing firms, determine the impact of pricing on the marketing of the product and ascertain the effect of product assortment on the marketing of the product in South East Nigeria. The area of the study was south east, Nigeria. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. The total population was three hundred and ninety four (394 employees). The whole population was used due small number. Three hundred and fifty four (354) questionnaires were returned and accurately filled. The validity of the instrument was tested using content analysis and the result was good. The reliability was tested using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r). It gave a reliability co-efficient of 0.78 which was also good. Data was presented and analyzed by mean score and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale. For the test of the hypotheses, the data were analyzed using F- statistics (ANOVA) statistic tool. The findings indicated that Product safety had significant positive effect on marketing firms in South East, Nigeria $F(95, n = 352), 224.701. P. <.05$. Pricing had significant positive impact on the marketing of the product in South East, Nigeria $F(95, n = 352), 161.971. P. <.05$ and Product assortment had significant positive effect on the marketing of the product in South East Nigeria $F(95, n = 352), 160.462. P. <.05$. The study concluded that Marketing ethics remains a complex area; although marketing practice has been brought into close conformity with prevailing ethical standards, marketing will be under pressure from organizational efforts to institutionalize formal ethics programs to satisfy stakeholder demands. The study recommended among others that the quality staff of the Commission both state and federal level should be employed for product safety for consumer's good health and to avoid a hazard.

Keywords: Marketing Ethics; Product Safety; Product Assortment

* Correspondence: ***.ogbuke@esut.edu.ng (available on request)
Department of Marketing, Enugu State University of Science and Technology
Enugu, Nigeria

© The Author(s) 2024. This article is open access and is governed by a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. You are free to use, share, adapt, distribute, or reproduce it in any medium or format, provided you give appropriate credit to the original author(s) and the source. A link to the Creative Commons license should be provided, and any changes made should be indicated. The article's Creative Commons license covers the images and other third-party materials, unless specified otherwise in a credit line. If your intended use goes beyond the permitted scope or is restricted by statutory regulations not covered by the license, you must seek permission directly from the copyright holder. For a detailed copy of the license, please visit <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>. The Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication waiver (<http://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/>) is applicable to the data presented in this article, unless stated otherwise in a credit line to the data.

Background of the Study

Marketing ethics are the moral principles and values that need to be followed during any marketing communication. They are the general set of guidelines which can aid companies to decide on their new marketing strategies. Marketing ethics promotes fairness and honesty in all their advertisements. Any false claims to the consumers, invading consumer's privacy, stereotyping and targeting the vulnerable audience (like children and elderly) are considered to be immoral behavior by the companies (Pranjal, 2018). Marketing ethics is an area of applied ethics which deals with the moral principles behind the operation and regulation of marketing. Some areas of marketing ethics (ethics of advertising and promotion) overlap with media ethics. There are certain high caution aspects of ethical marketing regarding market audience.

The functional area is most closely related to ethical abuse in firms is marketing. This is because marketing is the function of a business charged with communicating and openly satisfying customers (Volle. 2013). Thus, marketing is closest to the public view and, consequently, is subject to considerable societal analysis and scrutiny. Marketing is a critical functional area in the business organization that provides a visible interface with not only customers but with all other stakeholders. It is essential when addressing marketing ethics to recognize that it should be examined from an individual, organizational, and societal perspective. The Marketing ethics should be considered from an individual and organizational perspective. From the individual perspective personal values and moral philosophies are the key to ethical decisions in marketing (Dincer and Dincer, 2014).

Customers are treated like this because companies think that they are unprofitable, so they strive to deprive them or avoid them altogether. It is often debated amongst the business community that to be profitable; often businesses have to be unethical. However, this notion is seemingly outdated as most businesses nowadays follow an ethical business plan. Another breach of marketing ethics has to do with the use of deceptive advertising. This form of advertising is not specific to one target market, and can sometimes go unnoticed by the people. There are many different ways in which deceptive marketing can be presented to consumers; one of these methods is accomplished through the use of humor. Business ethics has been an increasing concern among larger companies, at least since the 1990s. Significant corporations increasingly scare the damage to their image associated with press revelations of unethical practices. Marketers have been among the fastest to perceive the market's preference for ethical firms, often moving faster to take advantage of this shift in consumer taste. This results in the expropriation of ethics itself as a selling point or a component of a corporate image (Palmer and Hedberg, 2012). Business ethics is one of the most complicated and contentious subjects in human history. Both academics and business leaders have studied the relationship between doing the right thing and making money for years with the little consensus reached. Companies realize the importance of acting more ethically and broadcasting this transformation to their customers. One of the most accessible means to achieve this is through their marketing practices. If a company makes an effort to advertise more ethically, it reflects positively on every area of that business (Silvia, 2014).

Statement of the Problem

Marketing ethics is an area of application that involves moral principles behind operation and regulation of marketing. Therefore, it is a process through which companies generate customer interest in products/services, create value for stakeholders and build strong customer relationships. Marketing ethics are ethical standards which pertain to marketing. Ethical marketing sets out the framework to provide customers with the excellent marketing practices. It refers to high standards which the organization follows to give the relative information to the customers about the product. It is a way to communicate with consumers positively so that they get the preferred information which they want. It is essential for a marketer to behave in a principled way with the customers so that he feels delighted with the service which he is offering.

Successful marketing is complicated in just about every trade, but the issues are compounded in the legal industry where firms, individuals, and companies are required to tread carefully as they adapt to changes both in the workplace and the marketplace. The challenge faced by marketing ethics includes poor product safety, reduced pricing on marketing products, poor product assortment. The most significant ethical problem in marketing and advertising is determining the exact ethical boundaries based on the industry. This will slightly differ based on production, and this is where a strong sense of ethics presents itself. Though the pursuit of ethical marketing does not automatically translate into increased profit, the firm still must ensure it is responsible for its actions and their impact on society.

Ethical issues in marketing arise from the conflicts and lack of agreement on particular issues. Parties involved in marketing transactions have a set of expectations about how the business relationships will take shape and how various operations need to be conducted. The business owner makes an ethical policy that serves the good of his employees and the good of the company. To resolve unethical situations in the future, ethics officers in organizations should be implemented to align practices of the workplace with ethics and beliefs of the workplace. Therefore, the study emphasized on to evaluate marketing ethics in South East Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The primary objective of the study was to assess marketing ethics in South East Nigeria. The specific goals include to:

1. Evaluate the effect of product safety on the marketing firms in South East, Nigeria.
2. Determine the impact of pricing on the marketing of the product in South East, Nigeria.
3. Ascertain the effect of product assortment on the marketing of the product in South East Nigeria

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

1. What is the impact of product safety on the marketing firms in South East, Nigeria?
2. What is the effect of pricing on the marketing of the product in South East, Nigeria?
3. What is the impact of product assortment on the marketing of the product in South East Nigeria?

Statement of Hypotheses

The following hypotheses will guide the study.

1. Product safety has no positive effect on marketing firms in South East, Nigeria.
2. Pricing has no positive impact on the marketing of the product in South East, Nigeria.
3. Product assortment has no positive effect on the marketing of the product in South East Nigeria.

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Framework

Marketing

Marketing is the study and management of exchange relationships. Marketing is the social process by which individuals and organizations obtain what they need and want through creating and exchanging value with others. Marketing is the process by which companies create value for customers and build strong customer relationships to capture value from customers in return. Marketing is the management process for identifying, anticipating and satisfying customer requirements profitably. Marketing is the activity, set of institutions, and procedures for creating, communicating, delivering, and exchanging offerings that have value for customers, clients, partners, and society at large (Kotler and Armstrong, 2010).

Ethics

Ethics are a collection of principles of right conduct that guides the decisions people or organizations make. Practicing ethics in marketing means deliberately applying standards of fairness, or moral rights and wrongs, to marketing decision making, behavior, and practice in the organization. Marketing ethics is the important principles and values that govern the business practices of those engaged in promoting products or services to consumers. Sound marketing ethics are typically those that result in or at least do not negatively affect consumer satisfaction with the goods and services being promoted or with the company producing them (Business Dictionary, 2018).

Marketing Ethics

Marketing ethics refer specifically to the application of this basic morality in the conduct of business with their consumers and other related parties. Such a practice must necessarily include a conscious attempt by the companies under consideration to applying moral principles when they are dealing with clients or other customers, especially when it comes to the 4 Ps, place, production, pricing and promotion of their goods or services. Marketing is a way of promoting your business in various ways (Taumata, 2017). Ethical marketing is less of a marketing strategy and more of a philosophy that informs all marketing efforts. It seeks to promote honesty, fairness, and responsibility in all advertising.

Product Safety and Marketing a Product

Product safety is a term used to describe policies designed to protect people from risks associated with thousands of consumer products they buy and use daily. There are some laws at the state and federal levels intended to protect buyers from unsafe consumer goods or potentially harmful elements found in many everyday products. The Commission works to ensure the safety of consumer products, especially those that pose a risk of fire, electrical, chemical, or mechanical hazard. In a well-run organization, marketing is responsible for determining market requirements. And in some markets, product safety is an essential requirement. (Andrea, 2018). Security can be a vital market requirement, and therefore, it is the responsibility of marketing to make sure that required regulations are identified, specific customer needs are reviewed and met, and the products are in compliance with relevant regulations. Marketing does not create or design products; however, marketing must be the place where all market requirements are identified (Hammond, 2018). In view of this the following hypothesis was formulated: H_i. Product safety has no positive effect on marketing firms in South East, Nigeria.

Pricing on a Product

No matter the type of product you sell, the price you charge your customers or clients will have a direct effect on the success of your business. Before setting a price for your product, you have to know the costs of running your business. If the price for your product or service doesn't cover expenses, your cash flow will be cumulatively negative, you'll exhaust your financial resources, and your business will ultimately fail. To determine how much it costs to manage your business, including property and equipment leases, loan repayments, inventory, utilities, financing costs, and salaries/wages/commissions. The most important is to add profit in your calculation of damages. Treat benefit as a fixed cost, as a loan payment or payroll, since none of us is in business to break even. Because pricing decisions require time and market research, the strategy of many business owners is to set prices once and hope for the best (Krista, 2017).

The Role of Product Assortment in Marketing

Product assortment is the collection of goods or services that a business provides to consumers. The significant characteristics of a company's product assortment are: (1) its length or number of products, (2) its breadth or amount of product lines, (3) its depth or amount of product varieties within a product line and (4) its consistency or how products relate to each other in a retail environment (Business Dictionary, 2018). It's the practice of having the right products, in the right place, at the right time, for the right customers. It has a focused assortment strategy that helps you carve out a clear position in today's saturated e-commerce market

Organizational Behaviour in Selling their Products

Organizational behavior defines how an organization is run, where it fits into a particular industry and what its future will hold. It is enormously important because the organization is at the core of what makes a company what it is, whether that company provides health care to millions of people or sells home goods at a tiny general store. Organizational behaviors outline the mission and goals of a business and define how its people interact with one another within its setting. But they also speak to where an organization fits into the bigger picture. To effectively sell a product or service, organizations have to know how consumers behave about what they buy (Miranda, 2018).

Theoretical Framework

The Contingency Theory in Management

The Contingency Theory has been widely accepted in management discipline since the early 60s. The theory emerged from the criticisms of the classical methods that advocates "one best way" of organizing and managing organizations. Contingency Theorists posit that there is no one best way to organize different organizations working in different industries and conditions. The appropriate management style and organizational structure depend on the environmental context of the organization concerned. One of the most influential studies in the emergence of the Contingency Theory is the work of Burns and Stalker (1971). They investigated the relationship between internal management practices and the external environment factors of 20 industrial organizations in the United Kingdom to discover its effect on economic performance. They found two different management practices in use, which they classified as "Mechanistic" and "Organic" systems. The Mechanistic System was appropriate for organizations that operated under stable conditions. These organizations employed routine and well-understood technology. Heads of departments clearly defined tasks and duties of employees. Communication within such organizations was designed vertically, and its content tended to be instructions from superiors.

Empirical Review

Okonkwo, (2014) conducted a study on the effect Of Global Manufacturing And Materials Management On Business Competitive Position In South East Nigeria. The objective of the study was on the Effect of Global Manufacturing and Materials Management on Business Competitive Position, in South East Nigeria. A survey design was adopted in the study. The population of the study was seven hundred and forty (740) staff of the five selected institutions in South East Nigeria. Taro Yamane formula was adopted in determining the sample size of 506. The sources of data were both primary and secondary. The reliability test of the instrument yielded a correlation coefficient of 0.97. All the hypotheses were statistically tested using the Z-test. At 5 percent level of significance, $Z_C = 47.554$, $Z_t > 1.645$; this indicated that there was a positive effect of global product manufacturing in Nigeria's business competitive position of selected institutions and firms in South East Nigeria. At 5 percent level of significance, the $Z_C = 47.554$, $Z_t > 1.645$; this indicated that there was a positive effect of global manufacturing planning on Nigeria trade competitive position of selected institutions in South East Nigeria. At 5 percent level of significance, $Z_C = 47.554$, $Z_t > 1.645$, this indicates that there was a positive effect of global manufacturing control on the competitive import position of the selected institutions in South East Nigeria. At 5 percent level of significance, the $Z_C = 47.554$, $Z_t > 1.645$, this indicated that there was a positive effect of the global production on the foreign direct investment competitive position of the selected institutions in South East Nigeria.

Gibson and Magdalena (2015) carried out a study on pricing strategies and customer retention: The case of Airtel (T) Ltd done under the consent of Airtel (T) Ltd with a major purpose of finding the correlation between pricing strategies and customer retention. This came about after a long term observation of customers who used to come in and out of Airtel (T) Ltd heading to other competitive companies in the Mobile Telecommunications industry. The Major reason for the shift was discovered to be the Price sensitivity as portrayed by the customers. It was identified that customers were willing to move to a company that offered mobile services at slightly lower price. Answers to the questions regarding the study were resolved through questionnaires that were filed by a number of employees that work for Airtel (T) Ltd who were involved in the daily running of the company and had a direct touch with the customers. After a thorough study of the given answers, a conclusion was drawn that there is a positive correlation between pricing strategies and customer retention and thus in order to retain as many customers as possible, Airtel needed to come up with better pricing strategies that will attract as many customers as possible.

Obasan, Ariyo, and Hassan (2015) carried out a study on marketing strategy and product performance: a study of selected firms in Nigeria. The study was conducted to investigate the nature of relationship between marketing strategy and product performance with a special focus on the food and beverage industry in Nigeria. The study used primary data gathered from 284 randomly selected staff of ten selected companies. These companies are quoted on the Nigerian stock exchange. To do this, a questionnaire was adopted as research instrument. The data gathered was subjected to factor analysis and regression analysis. The results show that indeed marketing strategy impacts product performance of the observed firms. More so, of all the factors considered (promotion strategy, Product strategy, Distribution strategy, General marketing strategy and Pricing Strategy) promotional factors were found to be most important, then product strategy while pricing mix account for the least variation. The study therefore recommended that business organisations should accord necessary attention to the element of marketing strategy by designing market strategies driven by a sound marketing management, targeting and strategic positioning.

Isiwu, Amusa, and Ugo (2016) conducted a study on the effects of climate change on food production and farm level adaptation practices in South-East Nigeria. The study investigated the impact of climate change on food production and farm level adaptation practices in South-east Nigeria. In carrying out the study, four research questions were developed and answered. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design to sample the opinion of 240 smallholder farmers from Enugu and the Imo States in South-east Nigeria. The instrument for data collection was a 76-item close-ended questionnaire structured into 4-point rating scale to answer the level of climate change awareness of farmers, the intensity of the effects of climate change on food production and adaptive practices by the farmers. The instrument was face-validated by three experts while Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficients of 0.81, 0.76, 0.79 and 0.73 were obtained for climate change awareness of farmers, effects of climate change on food production, adaptation practices in crop production and livestock production clusters respectively. Out of the 240 copies of the questionnaire administered to the farmers, 227 copies were retrieved and wholly filled representing 96% return rate. The data collected were analyzed using mean (\bar{x}). Based on the data collected and analyzed, the study found that farmers in southeast Nigeria are aware of climate change. The intensity of heat, prolonged drought, decreased rainfall amount, significant heavy rainfall, flooding, drying up of rivers, lakes, and streams among others were identified as severe effects of climate change on agricultural production in Southeast Nigeria. Despite these effects, the study also found that the adaptive capacity of smallholder farmers is still deficient.

Ifediora, Ugwuanyi, and Ifediora (2017) carried out a study on the perception and patronage of foreign products by consumers in Enugu, Nigeria. The study investigated understanding and support of foreign products. The specific objectives were: to ascertain if perceived risk level influences patronage of foreign goods; to determine if perceived value affects the sponsorship of foreign goods, and; to find out if the country of origin is a significant consideration when purchasing foreign products. The study population was all adults (18 years and above) in Enugu South Local Government Area of Enugu State, Nigeria out of which study sampled 400 consumers. The hypotheses were tested using Spearman's Correlation Coefficient. The findings show that there is a relationship between perceived risk and patronage of foreign products. Also, there is a positive relationship between perceived value and support of foreign products. Finally, the country of origin was found to be a significant consideration in the patronage of foreign products. The study concludes that perceived risk and state of birth affect Nigerian consumers' purchase of foreign products. Nigerian consumers tend to view foreign products as being superior to local products. The study recommends that local manufacturers should be quality conscious and consumer-focused, to compete effectively with imported products.

Mario and Kowalkowski (2017) investigated the development and current state of pricing strategy research by undertaking a content analysis of 515 articles published in leading academic journals between 1995 and 2016. Analyses were carried out using correlation and regression model. The results suggest several developments in research focus and methodology; recent research has focused more strongly on services and applies more rigorous research designs. The results also indicate a persistent focus on consumer markets and economic theories, as well as an increasing consideration of demand-side respondents, at the expense of supply-side respondents. An important feature of this review is a set of actionable takeaways, with both theoretical and methodological implications for pricing strategy research.

Summary and Gap in the Review of Related Literature

The study on marketing ethics in South East Nigeria has attracted a good number of empirical studies as seen above. Most of the evidence point out that researcher in this area is worth commending. Many of the studies reviewed did not review ethics as a variable. The few studies done in South East did not focus on Ibimo industries, Obi's shoes limited, Ngo bros limited, Ezenwa plastic industries, PZ plc, Unilever industries, and Innoson industries plc. The study therefore is moved is by the need to fill this gap marketing ethics in South East Nigeria. This is the high point of contribution to the study.

The section was summarized in the following sub-headings such as conceptual framework, theoretical framework and empirical review. Under conceptual framework all the concept were discussed in detail such as marketing, ethics, product safety, product assortment. The study was guided by the following theory: The contingency theory and Hunt–Vitell theory of marketing ethics (1986). The study was anchored on the Hunt-Vitell theory of marketing ethics. The prior studies were review under empirical studies.

Methodology

The area of the study was south east, Nigeria. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. The population consisted of selected 7 registered manufacturing firms in South-East Geo-political Zone of Nigeria which is made up of five states (Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu and Imo States) with a total population of three hundred and ninety four (394 employees). The whole population was used due small number. Three hundred and fifty four (354) questionnaires were returned and accurately filled. The validity of the instrument was tested using content analysis and the result was good. The reliability was tested using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r). It gave a reliability co-efficient of 0.800 which was also good. Data was presented and analyzed by mean score (3.0 and above agreed while below 3.0 disagreed) and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale. For the test of the hypotheses, the data were analyzed using F- statistics (ANOVA) statistic tool.

Data presentation and Analyses

Table 1: Response on the statement that product safety affects the marketing firms in South East, Nigeria.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Strongly agree	79	22.4	22.4
Agree	140	39.8	39.8
Neutral	56	15.9	15.9
Disagree	52	14.8	14.8
Strongly disagree	25	7.1	7.1
Total	352	100.0	100.0

From Table 1 indicated that 79 respondents out of 352 representing 22.4 percent strongly agree, 140 respondents representing 39.8 percent agree that the product safety affects the marketing firms in South East, Nigeria. 56 respondents representing 15.9 percent were neutral, 52 respondents representing 14.8 percent disagreed and 25 respondents representing 7.1 percent strongly disagree.

Table 2: Response on the statement that Pricing impacts on the marketing of the product in South East, Nigeria.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Strongly agree	96	27.3	27.3
Agree	51	14.5	14.5
Neutral	74	21.0	21.0
Disagree	52	14.8	14.8
Strongly disagree	79	22.4	22.4
Total	352	100.0	100.0

From Table 2, indicated that 96 respondents out of 352 representing 27.3 percent strongly agree, 51 respondents representing 14.5 percent agree that the Pricing impacts on the marketing of the product in South East, Nigeria. 74 respondents representing 21.0 percent were neutral, 52 respondents representing 14.8 percent disagreed and 79 respondents representing 22.4 percent strongly disagree.

Table 3: Response on the statement that product assortment effects the marketing of the product in South East Nigeria

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Strongly agree	169	21.6	21.6
Agree	399	51.4	51.4
Neutral	127	16.4	16.4
Disagree	20	2.6	2.6
Strongly disagree	61	7.9	7.9
Total	776	100.0	100.0

From Table 3 indicated that 169 respondents out of 169 representing 21.6 percent strongly agree, 399 respondents representing 51.4 percent agree that the nutritional concerns of a household as a factor that affects foodways in

Nigerian food marketing. 127 respondents representing 16.4 percent were neutral, 20 respondents representing 2.6 percent disagreed and 61 respondents representing 7.9 percent strongly disagree.

Test of Hypotheses

Test of hypothesis One: Product safety has no positive effect on marketing firms in South East, Nigeria

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. The error of the Estimate
1	.779 ^a	.777	.777	.06994

a. Predictors: (Constant), YOH,TIS,TPT,PPT

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	549.600	5	109.920	224.703	.000 ^b
	Residual	1.614	330	.005		
	Total	551.214	335			

a. Dependent Variable: TEOP
b. Predictors: (Constant), YOH,TIS,TP T,PPT

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.032	.014		2.254	.025
	YOH	.344	.009	.339	37.477	.000
	TIS	.323	.010	.305	32.380	.000
	TPT	.299	.011	.347	26.128	.000
	PPT	.091	.013	.101	7.090	.000

a. Dependent Variable: TOP

Where:

- TEOP = The effect of product safety on the marketing firms in South East, Nigeria
 YOH = Your organization has been in line with the compliance of state and national regulations
 TIS = There is the safety of products posed to a risk of fire in my firms
 TPT = The products that are posed to a chemical in my firms are protected
 PPT = Products posed to electrical risk in my organization is protected against hazards

Statistical Criteria {First Order Test}

The Coefficient of Multiple Determinants {r²}

The R² {R-Squared} which measures the overall goodness of fit of the complete regression, shows the value as .777 and adjusted to .777. This means that R² accounts for 77.7 percent approximately 78 percent. This indicates that the independent variables account for about 100 percent of the variation in the dependent variable. Which shows the goodness of fit?

The student's t-test:

The test is carried out, to check for the particular significance of the variables. Statistically, the t-statistics of the variables under consideration is interpreted based on the following statement of the hypothesis.

H₀: The individual parameters are not significant.

H₁: The individual parameters are significant.

Decision Rule:

If t-calculated > t-tabulated, we reject the null hypothesis {H₀} and accept the alternative hypothesis {H₁}, and if otherwise, we select the null hypothesis {H₀} and reject the alternative hypothesis {H₁}.

$$\text{Level of significance} = \alpha \text{ at 5percent} = \frac{0.05}{2} = 0.025$$

Degree of freedom: n-k

Where n: sample size.

K: Number of the parameter.

$$335-4 = 331 = 2.326$$

The calculated value for the t-test:

Table 7: The t-test is summarized in the table below:

Variables	t-cal	t-tab	Remark
(Constant)	2.254	± 2.326	Significant
YOH	37.477	± 2.326	Significant
TIS	32.380	± 2.326	Significant
TPT	26.128	± 2.326	Significant
PPT	7.090	± 2.326	Significant

The t-statistics are used to test for special significance of the estimated parameters. From the table above, we can infer that the following parameters were statistically significant, we now agree that Your organization has been in line with the compliance of state and national regulations; There is safety of products posed to a risk of fire in my firms; The products that are represented as chemical in my firms are protected and Products posed to electrical risk in my organization is protected against hazards

F-statistics (ANOVA)

The F-statistics is used to test for simultaneous significance of all the estimated parameters.

The hypothesis is stated;

$$H_0: \beta_1 = \beta_2 = \beta_3 = \beta_4$$

$$H_1: \beta_1 \neq \beta_2 \neq \beta_3 \neq \beta_4$$

Level of significance: α at 5 percent

$$\text{Degree of freedom: } \frac{k-1}{N-K} = \frac{4-1}{335-4} = (331, 3) = 2.7858$$

Decision Rule:

If the f-calculated is greater than the f-tabulated {f-cal > f-tab} reject the null hypothesis {H₀} that the overall estimate is not significant and if otherwise conclude that the overall estimate is statistically significant.

Decision

From the result, f-calculated {224.701} was greater than the f-tabulated {2.7858}, that is, f-cal > f-tab. Hence, we reject the null hypothesis {H₀} and accept alternate hypothesis which means that the overall estimate has a good fit

which also implies that our independent variables are simultaneously significant. We now conclude from the analysis that Product safety has the positive effect on marketing firms in South East, Nigeria.

Test of hypothesis Two

Pricing has no Positive Effect on the Marketing of the Product in South East, Nigeria.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. The error of the Estimate
1	.897 ^a	.895	.895	.09625

a. Predictors: (Constant), TPO, PIU, VOS, PDT.

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	600.199	4	150.050	161.979	.000 ^b
	Residual	3.066	331	.009		
	Total	603.265	335			

a. Dependent Variable: TEOP
b. Predictors: (Constant), TPO, PIU,VOS, PDT

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.060	.017		3.541	.000
	TPO	-.026	.012	-.026	-2.138	.033
	PIU,	.387	.013	.412	29.521	.000
	VOS	.263	.012	.264	21.212	.000
	PDT	.353	.012	.371	30.255	.000

a. Dependent Variable: TOP

Where:

- TEOP = The effect of pricing on the marketing of the product in South East, Nigeria
TPO = The price of a product or service determines its level of profit
PIU = Price is used for competitive advantages of a product
VOS = Volume of sales depends on price in my organization
PDT = Price determines the costs of running a business in my firm -

Statistical Criteria {first order test}

The Coefficient of Multiple Determinants {r²}

The R² {R-Squared} which measures the overall goodness of fit of the complete regression, shows the value as .895 and adjusted to .895. This means that R² accounts for 89.5 percent approximately 90 percent. This indicates that the independent variables account for about 100 percent of the variation in the dependent variable. Which shows the goodness of fit?

The Student's t-test:

The test is carried out, to check for the particular significance of the variables. Statistically, the t-statistics of the variables under consideration is interpreted based on the following statement of the hypothesis.

H₀: The individual parameters are not significant.

H₁: The individual parameters are significant.

Decision Rule:

If t-calculated > t-tabulated, we reject the null hypothesis {H₀} and accept the alternative hypothesis {H₁}, and if otherwise, we select the null hypothesis {H₀} and reject the alternative hypothesis {H₁}.

Level of significance = α at 5percent = $\frac{0.05}{2} = 0.025$

Degree of freedom: n-k

Where n: sample size.

K: Number of the parameter.

335-4 = 331 = 2.326

The calculated value for the t-test:

Table 11: The t-test is summarized in the table below:

Variables	t-cal	t-tab	Remark
(Constant)	3.541	± 2.326	Significant
TPO	-2.138	± 2.326	Significant
PIU,	29.521	± 2.326	Significant
VOS	21.212	± 2.326	Significant
PDT	30.255	± 2.326	Significant

The t-statistics are used to test for particular significance of the estimated parameters. From the table above, we can infer that the following parameters were statistically significant, we now agree that the price of a product or service determines its level of profit; Price is used for competitive advantages of a product; Volume of sales depends on price in my organization and price determines the costs of running a business in my firm -

F-statistics (ANOVA)

The F-statistics is used to test for simultaneous significance of all the estimated parameters.

The hypothesis is stated;

H₀: $\beta_1 = \beta_2 = \beta_3 = \beta_4$

H₁: $\beta_1 \neq \beta_2 \neq \beta_3 \neq \beta_4$

Level of significance: α at 5 percent

Degree of freedom: $\frac{k-1}{N-K} = \frac{4-1}{335-4} = (3, 331) = 2.7858$

Decision Rule:

If the f-calculated is greater than the f-tabulated {f-cal,> f-tab} reject the null hypothesis {H₀} that the overall estimate is not significant and if otherwise conclude that the overall estimate is statistically significant.

Decision

From the result, f -calculated {161.979} is greater than the f -tabulated {2.7858}, that is, f -cal > f -tab. Hence, we reject the null hypothesis $\{H_0\}$ and accept alternate hypothesis which means that the overall estimate has a good fit which also implies that our independent variables are simultaneously significant. We now conclude from the analysis that Pricing has a positive effect on the marketing of the product in South East, Nigeria.

Test Hypothesis Three

Product assortment has no positive effect on the marketing of the product in South East Nigeria

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. The error of the Estimate
1	.809 ^a	.799	.799	.03034

a. Predictors: (Constant), TPA, CCH, RHB, MIC

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	591.009	4	147.752	160.462.	.000 ^b
	Residual	.301	327	.001		
	Total	591.310	331			

a. Dependent Variable: TEAS
b. Predictors: (Constant), TPA, CCH, RHB, MIC

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.010	.006		-1.807	.072
	TPA	.222	.007	.219	33.499	.000
	CCH	.405	.009	.396	47.409	.000
	RHB,	.373	.007	.389	51.279	.000
	MIC	.001	.003	.001	.464	.643

a. Dependent Variable: TEAS

Where:

- TEAS = The effect of product assortment on the marketing of the product in South East, Nigeria
 TPA = The product assortment has assisted in retaining customers.
 CCH = Customers choice has been made possible through various sizes of the product
 RHB = Retailers have been forced to lower their prices due to varieties
 MIC = Multiple items can be purchased from a product category on a single purchasing trip

Statistical Criteria {first order test}

The Coefficient of Multiple Determinants $\{r^2\}$

The R^2 {R-Squared} which measures the overall goodness of fit of the complete regression, shows the value as .799 and adjusted to .799. This means that R^2 accounts for 79.9 percent approximately 80 percent. This indicates that the independent variables account for about 100 percent of the variation in the dependent variable. Which shows the goodness of fit?

The student's t-test:

The test is carried out, to check for the special significance of the variables. Statistically, the t-statistics of the variables under consideration is interpreted based on the following statement of the hypothesis.

H_0 : The individual parameters are not significant.

H_1 : The individual parameters are significant.

Decision Rule:

If t -calculated $>$ t -tabulated, we reject the null hypothesis $\{H_0\}$ and accept the alternative hypothesis $\{H_1\}$, and if otherwise, we select the null hypothesis $\{H_0\}$ and reject the alternative hypothesis $\{H_1\}$.

$$\text{Level of significance} = \alpha \text{ at 5percent} = \frac{0.05}{2} = 0.025$$

Degree of freedom: $n-k$

Where n : sample size.

K : Number of the parameter.

$$339-4 = 335 = 2.326$$

The calculated value for the t-test:

Table 15: The t-test is summarized in the table below:

Variables	t-cal	t-tab	Remark
TPA	-1.807	± 2.326	Significant
CCH	33.499	± 2.326	Significant
RHB	47.409	± 2.326	Significant
MIC	51.279	± 2.326	Significant
TPA	.464	± 2.326	Significant

The t -statistics are used to test for personal significance of the estimated parameters. From the table above, we can infer that the following parameters were statistically significant, we now agree that the product assortment has assisted in retaining customers; customers choice has been made possible through the various sizes of the product; retailers have been forced to lower their prices due to varieties, and Multiple items can be purchased from a product category on a single purchasing trip.

F-statistics (ANOVA)

The F-statistics is used to test for simultaneous significance of all the estimated parameters.

The hypothesis is stated;

$$H_0: \beta_1 = \beta_2 = \beta_3 = \beta_4$$

$$H_1: \beta_1 \neq \beta_2 \neq \beta_3 \neq \beta_4$$

Level of significance: α at 5 percent

$$\text{Degree of freedom: } \frac{k-1}{N-K} = \frac{4-1}{357-4} = (353, 3) = 2.7858$$

Decision Rule:

If the f -calculated is greater than the f -tabulated $\{f\text{-cal}, > f\text{-tab}\}$ reject the null hypothesis $\{H_0\}$ that the overall estimate is not significant and if otherwise conclude that the overall estimate is statistically significant.

Decision

From the result, f -calculated {160.462} is greater than the f -tabulated {2.7858}, that is, f -cal > f -tab. Hence, we reject the null hypothesis $\{H_0\}$ and accept alternate hypothesis which means that the overall estimate has a good fit which also implies that our independent variables are simultaneously significant. We now conclude from the analysis that Product assortment has a positive effect on the marketing of the product in South East Nigeria

Discussion of Findings

From the result, f -calculated {224.701} is greater than the f -tabulated {2.7858}, that is, f -cal > f -tab. Hence, it was concluded from the analysis that Product safety has a positive effect on marketing firms in the South East, Nigeria. Andrea (2018) support the result that there are some laws at the state and federal levels intended to protect buyers from unsafe consumer goods or potentially harmful elements found in many common products. The Commission works to ensure the safety of consumer products, especially those that pose a risk of fire, electrical, chemical, or mechanical hazard. In a well-run organization, marketing is responsible for determining market requirements. And in some markets, product safety is an important requirement.

In the literature review, Krista, (2013) asserts that pricing is one of the building blocks of marketing that appears to be easy to understand, but is probably one of the most difficult. Many think it is easy because we all buy products that have prices, and many believe all you have to do is sell the product for more than it costs the organization to earn a profit. The result supported the above assertion. Hence, f -calculated {161.971} is greater than the f -tabulated {2.7858}, that is, f -cal > f -tab. This shows that Pricing has a positive effect on the marketing of the product in South East, Nigeria.

From the result, f -calculated {160.462} is greater than the f -tabulated {2.7858}, that is, f -cal > f -tab. Hence, we reject the null hypothesis $\{H_0\}$ and accept alternate hypothesis which means that the overall estimate has a good fit which also implies that our independent variables are simultaneously significant. We now conclude from the analysis that Product assortment has a positive effect on the marketing of the product in South East Nigeria. The result was supported in the literature review by Steenkamp (2009) posits that Consumers often purchase multiple items from a product category on a single shopping trip. In doing so, they must frequently choose between items that are grouped into assortments, such as those offered by a particular store or brand.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Today, several forces are driving companies to practice a higher level of ethics: rising customer expectations, changing employee expectations, government legislation, and pressure, the inclusion of social criteria by investors, and evolving business procurement practices. Companies need to evaluate whether they are genuinely practicing ethical and socially responsible marketing. But unfortunately, most organizations define minimum acceptable ethical behavior and implement this level. While acceptable ethical conduct is derived from the professional, cultural, industry, and organizational environments, the individual behavior may differ based on moral judgments (Hunt and Vitell, 2005). Marketing ethics remains a complex area; although marketing practice has been brought into close conformity with prevailing ethical standards, marketing will be under pressure from organizational efforts to institutionalize formal ethics programs to satisfy stakeholder demands. Both normative and descriptive understanding will be required to improve marketing ethics. There are many opportunities to contribute to the advancement of knowledge in this critical area of marketing. In conclusion, this overview of marketing ethics provides a brief synopsis of the significant works in the field, and we encourage readers to draw their insights from these substantial works. The following recommendations were made:

- i. The quality staff of the Commission both state and federal level should be employed for product safety for consumer's good health and to avoid a hazard.
- ii. Fixing a price on the marketing of product firms should be careful not to place an amount that they would not be able to defend or below the quality of their product.
- iii. Product assortment on the marketing of product should be of importance to any firm to enable consumers to make their choice and be affordable.

References

- Adegbuyi, O. (2011). *Contemporary marketing strategies and performance of agricultural marketing firms in south-west Nigeria* [Doctoral dissertation, Covenant University, Ota, Ogun State, Nigeria].
- Afsar, B. (2014). Effect of perceived price, brand image, perceived quality and trust on consumer's buying preferences. *African Journal of Business Management*, 20(1), 1040–1047.
- Andrea, R. (2018). Product safety: Definition & concept. Retrieved from <https://study.com/academy/lesson/product-safety-definition-lesson-quiz.html>.
- Dietrich, R. (2018). The effect of consumer behavior in marketing of an organization. Retrieved from <https://smallbusiness.chron.com/effect-consumer-behaviour-marketing-organization-17934.html>.
- Dincer, C., & Dincer, B. (2014). An overview and analysis of marketing ethics. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 4(11), 1-8.
- Fatih, G. (2014). Examining price perception and the relationships among its dimensions via structural equation modeling: A research on Turkish consumers. *British Journal of Marketing Studies*, 2(1), 1–11.
- Francesca, D. M. (2014). Ethics in marketing. Retrieved from <https://www.monster.com/career-advice/article/ethics-in-marketing>.
- George, J. A., & Kostis, A. I. (2004). The impact of market structure on pricing objectives of service firms. *Journal of Product & Brand Management*, 13(5), 343–358.
- Gibson, G. N., & Magdalena, W. M. (2015). Pricing strategies and customer retention: The case of Airtel (T) Ltd [Master's thesis, International Business Option of Financial Management].
- Hague, P. N., Hague, N., & Morgan, C. A. (2013). *Market research in practice: How to get greater insight from your market*. London: Kogan Page.
- Ifediora, C. U., Ugwuanyi, C. C., & Ifediora, R. I. (2017). Perception and patronage of foreign products by consumers in Enugu, Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*, 4(12), 1-16.
- Ijeoma, U., Onodugo, O., & Ugwuonah, G. (2013). Effect of promotional strategies of pharmaceutical companies on doctors' prescription pattern in South East Nigeria. *TAF Preventive Medicine Bulletin*, 9(1), 1.
- Investopedia. (2018). Marketing. Retrieved from <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/m/marketing.asp>.
- Irefin, I. A., Olawale, G., & Onu, L. O. (2013). Effects of product pricing on business failure. *American International Journal of Contemporary Research*, 3(2).
- Isiwu, E. C., Amusa, T. A., & Ugo, P. (2016). Effects of climate change on food production and farm level adaptation practices in South-East Nigeria. Retrieved from <https://ecronicon.com/ecag/pdf/ECAG-03-000080.pdf>.
- Iyadi, R. C. (2015). Consumers' perception of safety of food in south-south and south-east Nigeria [Master's thesis, University of Nigeria Nsukka].
- Krista, F. (2013). Ways companies decide the price of a product. Retrieved from <https://www.businessinsider.com/3-powerful-pricing-strategies-businesses-should-always-consider-2013-10>.
- Krista, F. (2017). How to price a product: The ultimate product pricing strategy guide for small businesses. Retrieved from <https://fitsmallbusiness.com/product-pricing/>.
- Marketing-School.org. (2012). Ethical marketing. Retrieved from <http://www.marketing-schools.org/consumer-psychology.html>.
- Martin, L. H. (2018). Product safety – a marketing responsibility. Retrieved from https://www.questteam.com/resources/article.html?id=hammond_article_5.

- Mbah, P. C., Ukwuani, B. O., & Okonkwo, O. J. (2017). Effect of globalization on entrepreneurship development in South-East, Nigeria. *International Journal of Academic Research in Economics and Management Sciences*, 6(4).
- Miranda, M. (2018). How consumer behavior influences an organization. Retrieved from <https://smallbusiness.chron.com/consumer-behavior-influences-organization-31799.html>.
- Murphy, P. E. (1999). Character and virtue ethics in international marketing: An agenda for managers, researchers, and educators. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 18(1), 107–124.
- Obasan, K. A., Ariyo, O. O., & Hassan, B. A. (2015). Marketing strategy and product performance: A study of selected firms in Nigeria. *Ethiopian Journal of Environmental Studies and Management*, 8(6).
- Ogbuji, C. N., Anyanwu, A. V., & Onah, J. O. (2011). An empirical study of the impact of branding on consumer choice for regulated bottled water in Southeast, Nigeria. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 6(6), 1-17.
- Okonkwo, A. O. (2014). Effect of global manufacturing and materials management on business competitive position in South East Nigeria. Retrieved from http://Www.Unn.Edu.Ng/Publications/Files/17663_Effect_Of_Global_Manufacturing_Anmaterials_Management_On_Business_Competitive_Position_In_South_East_Nigeria.Pdf.
- Oluwole, M. S., & Ojekunle, J. A. (2016). Perceived environmental impact of refined petroleum products transportation and distribution: Case of Kaduna City, Nigeria. *FUTA Journal of Management and Technology Petroleum Products Transportation and Distribution*, 1(2), 112.
- Palmer, D., & Hedberg, T. (2012). The ethics of marketing to vulnerable populations. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 403-413.
- Pranjal, V. (2018). What are marketing ethics and its importance? Retrieved from <https://www.quora.com/What-is-marketing-ethics-and-its-importance>.
- Punished (Tracey, S. 2018). Marketing issues that have ethical implications. Retrieved from <https://smallbusiness.chron.com/marketing-issues-ethical-implications-24089.html>.
- Rachael, O. F. (2013). Consumers' buying decisions of foreign and domestic products in Nigeria: An analysis. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 5(25).
- Shewan, D. (2017). Ethical marketing: 5 examples of companies with a conscience. Retrieved from <https://www.wordstream.com/blog/ws/2017/09/20/ethical-marketing>.
- Solomon, O., & Adeyemi, O. O. (2012). Prevalence of counterfeiting in Nigeria: Evaluating consumers' experience in south-eastern and south-western Nigeria. *Global Journal of Human Social Science Sociology, Economics & Political Science*, 12(12).
- Taumata, J. T. (2017). What is marketing ethics and its importance? Self optimizing solution, analyze and optimize continuous. Retrieved from <https://www.quora.com/What-is-marketing-ethics-and-its-importance>.
- Wirawan, D. D. (2013). The effect of assortment changes on consideration set formation. *Contemporary Management Research*, 9(3), 231-246.